

Potentiometric investigations and effects of substituents on basicity of some acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type in acetonitrile and acetic acid

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Abstract : The basicity of the acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type, namely 1,5-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-salicylidene]-3-oxapentane (1), 1,5-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-methoxysalicylidene]-3-oxapentane (2), 1,5-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-bromosalicylidene]-3-oxapentane (3), 1,5-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-nitrosalicylidene]-3-oxapentane (4), 1,5-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamino]-3-oxapentane (5), 1,8-di[*N*-2-oxophenylsalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane (6), 1,8-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-methoxysalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane (7), 1,8-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-bromosalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane (8), 1,8-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-5-nitrosalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane (9), 1,8-di[*N*-2-oxophenyl-2-oxa-1-naphthylidenemethylamino]-3,6-dioxaoctane (10) was investigated potentiometrically in acetonitrile and acetic acid solvents. All compounds except one have shown rather well-shaped and stoichiometric titration curves in acetonitrile and acetic acid. The effect of substituents on basicities of these compound have been investigated. The orders of the basicity of substituents is H > OCH₃ > Br > NO₂.

Keywords : Potentiometry, Schiff base, acetonitrile, acetic acid.

Bis(imido) symmetrical and unsymmetrical Schiff base ligands and their complexes have been extensively studied¹. In this study, bis(imido) symmetrical Schiff base ligands (1-10)² have been titrated potentiometrically in acetonitrile and acetic acid solvents. Structures of substituted these compounds is given Scheme 1.

(R : H, OCH₃, Br and NO₂)

(n = 1 : 1, 2, 3 and 4)

(n = 2 : 6, 7, 8 and 9)

(n = 1 and 2)

(5 and 10)

Scheme 1. Structures of substituted bis(imido) symmetrical acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type compounds.

Results and discussion

In this study, bis(imido) Schiff bases were titrated

potentiometrically with perchloric acid. All compounds were given rather well-shaped and stoichiometric titration curves in acetic acid and acetonitrile solvents. Titration curves of these compounds are given in Figs. 1-4. From titration curves half-neutralization potentials (hnp, measures of their basicity) of the Schiff's bases were calculated. The half-neutralization potential values of the compounds are given in Table 1. The titration of these compounds with 0.02 M perchloric acid gave well shaped and stoichiometric end-points with potential jumps ranging from 100 to 200 mV (Figs. 1-4).

The potential jumps are considered to be good for potentiometric titrations. The half-neutralization potentials (hnp) mV for the 5-nitroSAL, NAP, 5-bromoSAL, 5-methoxySAL and SAL derivatives, respectively (higher values indicate a decrease and lower values an increase in basicity). Another important result obtained from these titrations curves is the one end-point of the bis(imido) Schiff bases. As can easily be seen, each -C=N- group is symmetrical structure of compounds. This means that two of the nitrogen atoms in a bis(imido) Schiff base molecule are protonated together. For instance, if the 5-hydrogen atom in Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxysalicylaldehyde (1 and 6) is replaced with a

Table 1. Half-neutralization potential values (hnp) of acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type in acetonitrile and acetic acid solvents at 25 °C

Comps.	Number	hnp (mV)	
		Acetonitrile	Acetic acid
1,5-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-salicylidene]-3-oxapentane	1	255	405
1,5-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-methoxysalicylidene]-3-oxapentane	2	276	412
1,5-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-bromosalicylidene]-3-oxapentane	3	288	415
1,5-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-nitrosalicylidene]-3-oxapentane	4	294	435
1,5-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamino]-3-oxapentane	5	290	425
1,8-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-salicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane	6	270	420
1,8-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-methoxysalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane	7	280	423
1,8-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-bromosalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane	8	292	428
1,8-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-5-nitrosalicylidene]-3,6-dioxaoctane	9	301	445
1,8-Di[N-2-oxyphenyl-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamino]-3,6-dioxaoctane	10	295	430

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of 0.001 M compounds (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) with perchloric acid in acetonitrile.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titration curves of 0.001 M compounds (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) with perchloric acid in acetic acid.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titration curves of 0.001 M compounds (6, 7, 8, 9, 10) with perchloric acid in acetonitrile.

Fig. 4. Potentiometric titration curves of 0.001 M compounds (6, 7, 8, 9, 10) with perchloric acid in acetic acid.

methoxy, bromo and nitro groups, the half-neutralization potential increases from 255–270 mV and 405–420 to 276–280 and 412–423, 288–292 and 415–428, 294–301 and 435–445 mV, respectively for acetonitrile and acetic acid. Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxySAL and 5-substitued-2-hydroxySAL are replaced 2-hydroxy-1-NAF (5 and 10), the half-neutralization potential increases from 255–270 and 405–420 to 290–295 and 425–430 mV, respectively for acetonitrile and acetic acid. This must be due to the even stronger electron-withdrawing power of the NAF groups than the SAL, 5-methoxySAL, 5-bromoSAL and electron releasing power of NAF than the 5-nitroSAL.

Finally, we were investigated effect of oxygen number of the poly ether ring on basicity. Another result obtained from these titration curves is the oxygen number of the poly ether ring. As can be seen from Table 1, decreasing basicity of acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 than 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. This means that decreasing basicity, with the increasing oxygen atom of the poly ether ring. This must except be due to an oxygen atom is electron-withdrawing from imine nitrogen.

Conclusion :

From the potentiometric titration of ten acyclic(polyether)s with Schiff base type in acetonitrile and acetic acid, the following result can be drawn. Two imine nitrogen atoms are equal. They can be titrated together with perchloric acid to give end-point in acetonitrile and acetic acid. This means that they are all in the same plane, and the whole system must be flat.

Experimental

Reagents :

All chemicals were of analytical-reagent grade and used without further purification. Salicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, DMF, THF, ethanol, 2-nitrophenol, hydrazine monohydrate and Pd-C (5%) were purchased from Merck (Germany) and was used as received. 1,5-Dichloro-3-oxapentane and 1,8-dichloro-3,6-dioxo octane were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. Acetonitrile and acetic acid were purchased from Merck and were used after purification³. Perchloric acid was purchased from Merck (70%) and was used as received. However, in order to remove its water content, it was prepared in ice-cooled acetic anhydride and left overnight and then diluted with solvents to prepare exactly 0.02 M solution of perchloric acid. These solutions

were standardized against a dry sodium acetate sample in each solvent⁴.

Apparatus :

An JENWAY 3010 Model pH meter equipped with a combined glass and Ag/AgCl electrode was used for the potentiometric titrations. Before use the aqueous solution of the Ag/AgCl electrode was emptied and refilled with a saturated solutions of KCl in dry methanol. All titrations were performed in a specially designed cell which is illustrated in reference⁵.

The cell was connected to a water-circulating thermostat in order to keep system at 25 ± 2 °C. The cell was made from Jena glass and had a capacity of 25 mL. The semi-micro burette enabled the titrant solution to be read to within 0.01 mL.

Procedure :

The compounds 1-10 were prepared according to the published procedure². 0.01 M Stock solutions from each Schiff's base in each solvent were prepared. From each solution 1.0 mL aliquat was taken by a calibrated pipette into a titration cell and then its volume was made up 10.0 mL by adding its pure solvent, and then was titrated with perchloric acid. Each time, before starting a titration pH meter was calibrated pH = 7 by using a buffer solution (pH = 7 corresponds to -17 mV in mV scale).

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